

**PS-1, PS-2 VA PS-3 POLIFENOLLARINING AORTA SILLIQ
MUSKULI PREPARATIGA VAZORELAKSANT TA'SIRIDA
SARKOPLAZMATIK RETIKULUM RIANODIN RETSEPTORINING
ISHTROKININI BAHOLASH**

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***Annotatsiya.** Tadqiqotlarda *Euphorbia farnchetii* turiga mansub bo'lgan o'simliklardan ajratib olingan 1-O-galloil-6-O-bisgalloil-2,4-valoneil- β -D-glyukoza (PS-1), 1-O-galloil-2,3-geksagidroksidifenoil-4,6-valoneil- β -D-glyukoza (PS-2) va 1,4,6 tri-O-galloil-2,3-valoneil- β -D-glyukoza (PS-3) polifenol birikmalarining izometrik sharoitda kalamush aorta qon-tomir silliq muskuli preparati qisqarish faolligiga vazorelaksant ta'sirini ta'minlanishida sarkoplazmatik retikulum rianodin retseptorining ishtroki baholangan. Tajribalarda tekshirilayotgan polifenollarning aorta silliq muskuli qisqarishlariga vazorelaksant ta'siri sarkoplazmatik retikulum (SR)ning rianodin retseptori (RyR) orqali chiquvchi Ca^{2+} -ionlarini kamayishi aorta silliq muskuli hujayralari sitozolida Ca^{2+} -ionlarini kamayishiga olib kelgan va buning natijasida qisqarish kuchini kamayishi kuzatilgan.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** sarkoplazmatik retikulum, rianodin retseptori, Ca^{2+} -kanallari, Ca^{2+} -ionlari, polifenol, qon tomir, silliq muskul, aktivator, kofein.*

***Аннотация.** В исследованиях оценивалось участие риадинового рецептора саркоплазматического ретикулаума в вазорелаксирующем эффекте полифенольных соединений 1-О-галлоил-6-О-бисгаллоил-2,4-валонеил- β -D-глюкозы (PS-1), 1-О-галлоил-2,3-гексагидроксицифеноил-4,6-валонеил- β -D-глюкозы (PS-2) и 1,4,6-три-О-галлоил-2,3-валонеил- β -D-глюкозы (PS-3), выделенных из растений вида *Euphorbia farnchetii*, на сократительную активность гладких мышц сосудов аорты крысы в изометрических условиях.*

Было обнаружено, что вазорелаксирующий эффект полифенолов, использованных в экспериментах на сокращениях гладких мышц аорты, обусловлен снижением ионов Ca^{2+} , высвобождаемых через рианодинорный рецептор (RyR) саркоплазматического ретикулума (SR), что приводит к снижению ионов Ca^{2+} в цитозоле клеток гладких мышц аорты, что приводит к снижению силы сокращения.

Ключевые слова: саркоплазматический ретикулум, рианодинорный рецептор, каналы Ca^{2+} , ионы Ca^{2+} , полифенол, кровеносный сосуд, гладкие мышцы, активатор, кофеин.

Annotation. The studies evaluated the involvement of the sarcoplasmic reticulum ryanodine receptor in the vasorelaxant effect of the polyphenol compounds 1-O-galloyl-6-O-bisgalloyl-2,4-valoneyl- β -D-glucose (PS-1), 1-O-galloyl-2,3-hexahydroxydiphenoyl-4,6-valoneyl- β -D-glucose (PS-2), and 1,4,6 tri-O-galloyl-2,3-valoneyl- β -D-glucose (PS-3) isolated from plants of the *Euphorbia farnchettii* species on the contractile activity of rat aortic vascular smooth muscle under isometric conditions. In the experiments, the vasorelaxant effect of the polyphenols tested on aortic smooth muscle contractions was observed to be due to the reduction of Ca^{2+} ions released through the ryanodine receptor (RyR) of the sarcoplasmic reticulum (SR) leading to a decrease in Ca^{2+} ions in the cytosol of aortic smooth muscle cells, which resulted in a decrease in the force of contraction.

Key words: sarcoplasmic reticulum, ryanodine receptor, Ca^{2+} channels, Ca^{2+} ions, polyphenol, blood vessel, smooth muscle, activator, caffeine.

Kirish. Silliq muskul hujayralari sarkoplazmatik retikulum (SR) Ca^{2+} -transport tizimlari ya'ni rianodin retseptori (RyR) va inozitol-1,4,5-trisfosfat retseptori (IP_3R) hamda Ca^{2+} -ATFaza (SERCA) asosan silliq muskul hujayra (SMH)lari Ca^{2+} gomeostazining regulyatsiyasida muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi [1,2]. SERCA faolligi orqali Ca^{2+} gomeostazida va hujayra ichki $[Ca]_{in}$ konsentratsiyasini kamaytirishda ishtirok etadi.

Shuningdek, SERCA orqali Ca^{2+} -ionlarining konsentratsiyasi kamaytiriladi va silliq muskul hujayralarining bo'shashishiga olib keladi [3]. IP_3 retseptorlari - yoki rianodin retseptorlari (RyR) – sarkoplazmatik retikulumdan sitozolga Ca^{2+} -ionlarining chiqishini ta'minlovchi kanallar hisoblanadi [4]. IP_3 retseptorlarining stimulyatsiyasi natijasida sitozolda Ca^{2+} -ionlarining konsentratsiyasi ortadi va qisqarish yuzaga keladi.

Kalsiy spark (chaqnash) sarkoplazmatik retikulumdagi rianodin retseptorlari (RyR) orqali kalsiyning, tez va vaqtinchalik chiqish hodisalarini ifodalaydi. Qon tomir SMHlarida kalsiyning chaqnashi K_{Ca} -kanallarning faollashishiga olib keladi va

umumiy hujayra ichidagi hajmining kamayishi kuzatiladi va vazokonstriksiyaning oldini oladi. Bu yurak va skelet muskullaridan farqli o'laroq, bu yerdan kalsiy sparkning fazoviy va vaqtinchalik yig'indisi miotsitlar qisqarishining keskin ortishiga olib keladi. Shunga ko'ra, qon tomir SMHlarining L-tipidagi Ca^{2+} -kanallar hujayra ichidagi kalsiy zahiralari regulyatsiya qiladi va bu esa o'z navbatida SRdan RyR orqali Ca^{2+} -ionlarining chiqishini modulyatsiya qiladi [5]. SMHlari RyR faolligi ko'ndalang-targ'il muskul hujayralariga qaraganda qarama-qarshi jarayon hisoblanadi [6].

Umuman olganda SMHlari SRning ikki xil turdagi Ca^{2+} chiqarish kanallari mavjud, ya'ni inozitol-1,4,5-trifosfat retseptorlari (IP_3R) va rianodin retseptorlari (RyR) bilan ta'minlangan. Odatda, ikkala Ca^{2+} -kanallari ham SMHlari Ca^{2+} deposidan sitozolga Ca^{2+} -ionlarining chiqishini mobilizatsiya qiladi. Kofein ishtroki orqali ta'minlangan aorta silliq muskuli qisqarish kuchining amplitudasi SRdagi mavjud barcha Ca^{2+} -ionlarining miqdoriy ko'rsatkichi hisoblanadi.

Material va metodlar

Aorta qon tomir preparatini tayyorlash standart uslub yordamida amalga oshirildi.

Tajribalar standart ozuqa va suv bilan ta'minlangan sharoitda boqilgan, sog'lom oq, zotsiz kalamushlarda (150–200 gr.) amalga oshirildi. Tajriba hayvonlari servikal dislokatsiya usulida jonsizlantirilgandan keyin, ko'krak qafasini jarrohlik usulida ochilib, aorta qon tomiri ajratib olindi va Krebs–Xenzelayt fiziologik eritmasi muhitida biriktiruvchi to'qimadan tozalanib, halqasimon segmentlar ($l=2-4$ mm; $\varnothing=1-2$ mm) shaklida kesildi. Tajriba yacheykasida (5 ml) doimiy ravishda quyidagi kimyoviy tarkibga ega bo'lgan Krebs-Xenzeleyt fiziologik eritmasi sirkulyatsiyalandi (mM hisobida): NaCl – 120,4; KCl – 5; $NaHCO_3$ – 15,5; NaH_2PO_4 – 1,2; $MgCl_2$ – 1,2; $CaCl_2$ – 2,5; $C_6H_{12}O_6$ – 11,5 (pH=7,4). Fiziologik eritma karbogen (O_2 -95% va CO_2 -5%) bilan aeratsiyalandi, harorat doimiyligi ($t=+37\pm 0,5^\circ C$) ultratermostat (U-8; Bolgariya) yordamida ta'minlandi. Aorta qon tomir preparatining qisqarish faolligi izometrik sharoitda FT-03 (Grass Instrument Co., AQSh) kuch sensori, signal kuchaytirgich qurilma (Grass Instrument, AQSh) orqali Endim 621.02 samopisesida (Chexiya) standart uslub (mexanografiya) yordamida qayd qilindi. Tajribalarda fenilefrin (1 mkM), fentolamin (10 mkM), $NaHCO_3$, $CaCl_2$, $MgSO_4$, glyukoza, NaCl, KCl, NaH_2PO_4 (Rossiya) reaktivlaridan foydalanildi.

Olingan natijalar OriginPro v. 8.5 SR1 (EULA, Northampton, MA 01060–4401, AQSh) maxsus dastur paketi yordamida statistik qayta ishlandi. Natijalar Lakin G.F. (1990) tomonidan keltirilgan uslublar yordamida matematik–statistik qayta ishlandi. Natijalar n marta takroriylikda amalga oshirilgan tajribalar natijalarining $M\pm m$ shaklida keltirilgan bo'lib, M – o'rtacha arifmetik qiymat va m – standart xatolik

qiymatini ifodalaydi. Shuningdek, tajriba natijalari guruhlar o'rtasidagi qiymatlarning statistik ishonchlilik darajasi Styudent t-mezone asosida hisoblandi va $p < 0,05$, $p < 0,01$ qiymatlarda statistik ishonchli deb baholandi. Dastlab, kalamush aorta preparati 1 gr (9,8~10 mN) kuchlanish berish asosida, ~45-60 minut davomida me'yoriy elektromexanik faollik qayd qilinishga qadar inkubatsiyalandi.

Olingan natijalar va ularning tahlili

Biz tajribalarmizda SRdan RyR orqali Ca^{2+} -ionlarini chiqishiga polifenollarning ta'sirini tekshirish uchun RyRning aktivatori hisoblangan – kofeindan foydalandik. Kofein aorta silliq muskul hujayrasi SR RyRga ta'sir etib u orqali Ca^{2+} -ionlarini sitozolga chiqarib qisqarishni vujudga keltiradi. Kofein 10 mM konsentratsiyada aorta muskul preparatida $72,1 \pm 4,8\%$ teng bo'lgan qisqarishni vujudga keltirdi. Ushbu kofein ta'sirida vujudga kelgan ($72,1 \pm 4,8\%$) aorta muskuli qisqarishlariga PS-1 (5-40 mkM) va PS-2 (5-25 mkM) polifenollarining konsentratsiyaga bog'liq ta'sirini kuzatganimizda (1-rasm A va B) PS-1 polifenoli 40 mkMda $21,9 \pm 3,6\%$ ga PS-2 polifenoli 25 mkMda $29,4 \pm 3,2\%$ ga kamaytirishi aniqlandi.

1-rasm. PS-1 (A) va PS-2 (B) polifenollarining kofein bilan chaqirilgan kalamush aortasi qisqarishiga dozaga bog'liq relaksant ta'siri. FE (1 mkM) yordamida chaqirilgan aorta qisqarishi nazorat sifatida 100% deb olingan (barcha holatlarda ishonchlilik ko'rsatkichi $p < 0,05$ $n=4$).

Shuningdek keyingi bosqich tajribalarimizda PS-3 (25-200 mkM) polifenolini kofein ta'sirida vujudga kelgan ($72,1 \pm 4,8\%$) aorta muskuli qisqarishlariga ta'siri

tekshirilganda kofein ta'sirida vujudga kelgan qisqarish kuchini $31,5 \pm 4,3\%$ ga kamaytirishi kuzatildi (2-rasm).

2-rasm. PS-3 polifenolining kofein bilan chaqirilgan kalamush aortasi qisqarishiga dozaga bog'liq relaksant ta'siri. FE 1 mkM yordamida chaqirilgan aorta qisqarishi nazorat sifatida 100% deb olingan (barcha holatlarda ishonchlilik ko'rsatkichi $p < 0,05$ $n=4$).

Yuqorida keltirilgan tajribalarga to'liq ishonch hosil qilish va yanada oydinlik kiritish maqsadida keyingi tajribalarmizda kofein yordamida chaqirilgan aorta muskuli qisqarishlariga polifenollarni ta'sir mexanizmlarini aniqlashda inkubatsiya muhitida Ca^{2+} -ionlarisiz sharoitda ularni ta'siri tekshirib ko'rildi. Tajribalarmizda $Ca^{2+}=0$ sharoitda kofein yordamida chaqirilgan aorta muskuli qisqarish kuchi $37,4 \pm 3,9\%$ ga teng bo'ldi.

Muhitda tekshirilayotgan polifenollar mavjud sharoitda ya'ni polifenollarni oldindan inkubatsiyalash sharoitda kofein yordamida chaqirilgan qisqarishlarni kamayishi kuzatildi (3-rasm). Tajribalarda PS-1 40 mkM, PS-2 25 mkM va PS-3 200 mkM inkubatsiyasi sharoitda kofein yordamida chaqirilgan qisqarish kuchi $37,4 \pm 3,9\%$ dan mos ravishda $16,1 \pm 2,8\%$, $23,6 \pm 3,2$ va $27,2 \pm 3,4\%$ ga kamayishi kuzatildi. Ushbu tajriba natijalari kofein ta'sirida SR RyR orqali chiquvchi Ca^{2+} -ionlarini aorta silliq muskuli hujayrasi membranasida joylashgan Ca^{2+} -transport tizimlari orqali tashqariga chiqarib yuborilishini ko'rsatadi.

3-rasm. Muhitda PS-1, PS-2 va PS-3 polifenollari mavjud shariotda Krebs eritmasi tarkibida $[Ca^{2+}] = 0$ holatda kofein bilan chaqirilgan kalamush aortasi qisqarishiga ta'siri. PS-1 (40 mkM), PS-2 (25 mkM) va PS-3 (200 mkM) polifenollari mavjud sharoitda Krebs eritmasi tarkibida $Ca^{2+} = 0$ mM holatda kofein (10 mM) yordamida chaqirilgan aorta qisqarishi. Muskel qisqarish kuchi nazorat sifatida 100% deb olingan (barcha holatlarda ishonchlilik ko'rsatkichi $p < 0,05$ $n = 4$).

Xulosa. Olingan natijalarning tahlili, tekshirilayotgan polifenollarni aorta silliq muskuli preparatiga vazorelaksant ta'siri SRning RyR orqali Ca^{2+} -ionlarini chiqishini kamaytirishi bilan bog'liq ekanligidan dalolat beradi. Shuningdek, tekshirilayotgan polifenollar ta'sirida SRdan Ca^{2+} -ionlarini chiqishini kamayishi aorta silliq muskuli hujayralari sitozolida Ca^{2+} -ionlarini kamayishiga olib keladi va buning natijasida qisqarish kuchini kamayishi kuzatiladi. Demak, tajriba natijalaridan ko'rinib turibdiki, tekshirilayotgan polifenollarning aorta silliq muskuli qisqarishlariga vazorelaksant ta'siri SRdan chiquvchi Ca^{2+} -ionlarini kamayishi bilan amalga oshib, bu ularning vazorelaksant ta'sirini yuzaga keltiradi.

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